

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Aquaculture and Fisheries

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Review article

Hurdle technology for fish preservation

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Hurdles
Fish
Quality
Safety
Kinetic modelling
Shelf life

ABSTRACT

Fresh fish is a highly perishable product due to the chemical composition of fish flesh and the high microbial load on fish surface. The natural microflora that is more adapted to low temperatures results also in lower thermal bacterial shock from natural temperature to the preservation temperature range. The development of new fish processing (e.g. high hydrostatic pressure, osmotic dehydration, high-intensity pulsed light) and packaging (e.g. modified atmospheres, active and intelligent packaging) methods or novel combinations of existing technologies is sought by the industry in the pursuit of producing alternative products, achieving shelf life extension, and management and reducing food waste. In 2014, processed fish was among the most active new product categories. The lack of dissemination of validated laboratory results for the seafood industry is one of the major issues preventing the uptake of minimal and nonthermal processing for fresh fish. However, it has been reported that some bacteria become more resistant under stress (e.g. psychrotolerant lactobacilli). At the same time, the application of some processing methods (e.g. thermal processing) may affect significantly the nutritional and sensory profile of the target food product. The application of several “soft hurdles” may reduce the rate of fish deterioration and spoilage caused by microbial growth. The objective of this article is to review the preservative effect of alternative hurdles on fish quality and shelf life, focusing on recent, combined applications.

1. Hurdles in fish preservation

World per capita fish consumption increased from an average of 9.9 kg in the 1960s to 14.4 kg in the 1990s and 19.7 kg in 2013, with estimates for 2014 and 2015 pointing towards further growth beyond 20 kg (FAO, 2016). However, fish is an extremely perishable product with high commercial value if its shelf life could be extended by application of appropriate processing and/or packaging technologies (Tsironi & Taoukis, 2018). Besides the short shelf life, another barrier to fresh fish consumption is represented by the consideration of seafood products as time-consuming meals (Corbo et al., 2009). Spoilage of refrigerated and lightly preserved fish is attributed mainly to microbial activity (Gram & Huss, 1996). In most cases, fish and fish products must be refrigerated or even frozen immediately after harvesting, in order to inhibit microbial growth and quality deterioration. In general, post-harvest processing technologies aim to overcome the short shelf life of fresh fish to improve commercialization and optimize resource utilization (e.g. fish filleting by-products). Several traditional food preservation methods (e.g. freezing, marinating, canning, salting etc.) are used to control the growth of microorganisms and delay spoilage of fish

products. Nonthermal processing has been introduced as an alternative to thermal treatment for foods, which would be negatively affected by even a mild temperature increase (Albertos et al., 2017; Chotphruethipong, Aluko, & Benjakul, 2019; Tsironi et al., 2019). However, each one of the applied factors has an optimum to minimum level influencing the microorganisms. This appropriate minimum level of the abovementioned factors may have a detrimental effect on other quality parameters, for example appearance, taste and odour and thus affect the consumer acceptability. For example, the incorporation of carvacrol (the main active compound of oregano) in the formulation of a fish product could serve as an effective antimicrobial. However, the required concentration that results in significant microbial growth inhibition and shelf life extension may detrimentally affect fish odour and taste (Tsironi & Taoukis, 2012). Nowadays, the consumer demands fresh or minimally processed foods of high quality, more “natural”, produced with the minimum amount of additives, microbiologically safe, nutritious and healthy (Erkmen & Bozoglu, 2016, pp. 166–179). Hurdle technology advocates the deliberate combination of existing and novel preservation techniques in order to establish a series of preservative factors (hurdles) that microorganisms are unable to

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aaf.2020.02.001>

Received 28 May 2019; Received in revised form 31 January 2020; Accepted 6 February 2020

Available online 29 February 2020

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Fig. 1. An example of the hurdle effect in fish preservation.

overcome, as illustrated in Fig. 1 (Leistner & Gorris, 1995). The most important hurdles used in food preservation are temperature (high or low), water activity (a_w), acidity (pH), redox potential (E_h), preservatives (e.g. nitrite, sorbate, surfit) and competitive microorganisms (e.g. lactic acid bacteria). However, according to Leistner (2000), more than 60 potential hurdles for foods, which improve the stability and/or quality of the products, have been described and the list of possible hurdles for food preservation is by no means complete. The individual hurdles may be encountered simultaneously or sequentially, depending on the type of hurdle and the overall processing (Leistner & Gorris, 1995). The application of this concept (referred also as combined processes, combination preservation or barrier technology) has been proved as very successful since the intelligent combination of hurdles secures the microbial stability and safety as well as sensory, nutritive and economic properties of a product. This sometimes leads to completely different product with its own new sensory characteristics.

In any case, the selection of the appropriate hurdles for a specific food product is of major importance. For example, one should consider that the heat resistance of bacteria increases at low a_w values and decreases when some preservatives are present, or that fermented meat based products may be considered as safe and stable if both a_w and pH values are within an appropriate range. The combination of new hurdles with conventional ones shows the potential to further preserve quality and extend the shelf life of food products (Erkmen & Bozoglu, 2016, pp. 166–179).

In the case of perishable products such as fish, low temperatures are the major and sometimes the only hurdle applied. However, if fish is exposed at abused temperatures during distribution and storage, this hurdle breaks down resulting in quality deterioration and increased safety risks, as for example histamine poisoning for scombroid fish and *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* growth in oysters, which are strongly correlated with increased storage temperatures (FAO/WHO, 2013, 2011; Tsironi, Ronnow, Giannoglou, & Taoukis, 2017).

The present review article aims to present the alternative hurdles that may be applied on fish and fish products in order to inhibit microbial growth and thus extend their shelf life. The basic applications of conventional and trivial technologies may be combined with advanced, modern food preservation techniques in order to improve quality and extend shelf life with the minimum effect on the nutritional and sensory profile of the final fish product. This article may inform the fish processing sector on the available food processing technologies that may be applied as “hurdles” for fish spoilage during distribution and storage. At the same time, the article aims to offer the researchers a comprehensive understanding on state of the art, in order to develop novel and effective combinations of food preservation methods to better retain fish quality and ensure the production of safe, high quality and nutritious fish products.

2. Mechanisms of antimicrobial effect of hurdles

Food preservation implies putting microorganisms in a hostile environment, in order to inhibit their growth or shorten their survival or cause their death. The feasible responses of microorganisms to this hostile environment determine whether they may grow or die. More research is needed in view of these responses; however further studies focused on considering the homeostasis, metabolic exhaustion and stress reactions of microorganisms in relation to hurdle technology, as

well by introducing the novel concept of multitarget preservation for a gentle but most effective preservation of hurdle-technology foods (Leistner, 2000).

2.1. Homeostasis

Homeostasis is the tendency to uniformity and stability in the internal status of organisms. In food preservation, the homeostasis of microorganisms is a key phenomenon which deserves much attention, because if the homeostasis of these microorganisms is disturbed by preservative factors (hurdles) in foods, they are not capable to multiply, i.e. they remain in the lag-phase or even die, before homeostasis is re-established (Leistner, 2000). However, microorganisms can undergo many important homeostatic reactions. Therefore, the most effective way to disturb homeostatic mechanisms is the combined application of multiple factors (hurdles). Repair for retaining a disturbed homeostasis is energy demanding, for this reason the restriction of energy supply inhibits repair or retaining mechanisms of the microbial cells and may have a synergistic antimicrobial effect. For example, the microorganisms living in a pH-variable food expend effort to retain their internal pH within very narrow limits. Another important homeostasis mechanism is the regulation of the internal osmotic pressure (osmohomeostasis), based on which the cells maintain a positive pressure by retaining the osmolarity of the cytoplasm higher than the cell environment, providing this regulation with the production of osmoprotective compounds, such as proline and betaine (Erkmen & Bozoglu, 2016, pp. 166–179).

2.2. Metabolic exhaustion

Metabolic exhaustion of microorganisms is another phenomenon of practical importance, which may cause “autosterilization” of foods (Leistner, 2000). It was first observed during experiments of mild thermal processing (95 °C) of liver sausages adjusted at different a_w values by the addition of salt and fat, for the inactivation of inoculated *Clostridium sporogenes*. Clostridial spores which survived the thermal treatment were not detected in the final product after storage at ambient temperature (Leistner et al., 1970). The most likely explanation is that bacterial spores which survive the thermal treatment are able to germinate in similar food products under less favourable conditions than those under which vegetative bacteria are able to multiply (Leistner, 1992). For this reason, the spore counts in stable hurdle preserved foods actually decrease during storage, especially at ambient temperatures. Another example is *Listeria* which decreases faster in water-in-oil emulsions (resembling the margarine) at room temperature than in refrigeration conditions. Under this context, storage at low temperatures is not always beneficial for the microbial stability of food products. Metabolic exhaustion is accelerated when multiple hurdles are applied and this may increase energy demands to maintain homeostasis under stress conditions, resulting in microbial cell damage (Erkmen & Bozoglu, 2016, pp. 166–179).

2.3. Stress reactions

It has been reported that some bacteria become more resistant or even more virulent under stress, since they generate stress shock proteins. The synthesis of protective stress shock proteins is induced by heat, pH, a_w , ethanol, oxidative compounds, etc. as well as by starvation. Stress reactions might have a non-specific effect. Microorganisms may become more tolerant to other stresses due to a particular stress, i.e. they acquire a “cross-tolerance”. The various responses of microorganisms under stress might hamper food preservation and could turn out to be problematic for the application of hurdle technology. On the other hand, the activation of genes for the synthesis of stress shock proteins, which help organisms to cope with stress situations, should be more difficult if different stresses are received at the same time.

Simultaneous exposure to different stresses will require energy-consuming synthesis of several or at least much more protective stress shock proteins, which in turn may cause the microorganisms to become metabolically exhausted. Therefore, multitarget preservation of foods could be the key to avoiding synthesis of stress shock proteins, which otherwise could jeopardize the microbial stability and safety of hurdle-preserved foods (Leistner, 2000).

2.4. Multitarget preservation

The concept of multitarget preservation of foods has been introduced by Leistner (1995). Multitarget preservation of foods should be the ambitious goal for a gentle but most effective preservation of foods. It has been suspected for some time that different hurdles in a food might not have just an additive effect on microbial stability, but they could act synergistically. A synergistic effect could be achieved if the hurdles in a food hit, at the same time, different targets (e.g. cell membrane, DNA, enzyme systems, pH, a_w , Eh) within the microbial cells and thus disturb the homeostasis of the microorganisms present in several respects. If so, the repair of homeostasis as well as the activation of stress shock proteins become more difficult (Leistner, 2000).

3. Hurdle preserved fish products

In the case of fish products manufactured in industrialized countries, hurdle technology has been reported as of major interest for the following applications:

- a) Convenience products based on traditional preparations, such as rehydrated salt-cured or dried fish. In this case, the raw material is a preserved semi-finished product, but since the preservative factor is removed at the processing stage, pathogens may survive and recover. Minimizing the survival of pathogens is therefore, beside the hygienic process conditions, necessary to ensure product safety.
- b) Lightly preserved fish products, which are uncooked or mildly cooked products, with low level of preservatives ($\text{NaCl} < 6\%$, $\text{pH} > 5$), such as cold-smoked salmon, carpaccio, slightly cooked shrimp, etc. These products are usually produced from fresh fish and seafood and further processing involves one or more additional steps that increase risk of cross contamination. The application of the different treatments are usually not sufficient to destroy pathogens, and since several of these products are ready-to-eat, minimizing the presence and prevent growth of pathogens is essential for food safety (Leroi et al., 2006, pp. 399–425).

The selected processing, packaging and preservation methods will definitely affect the spoilage mechanism and the major quality deterioration factors of a specific fish product. For example, in the case of cold smoked fish (where the combination of hurdles includes salt addition, mild thermal treatment and storage at low temperatures) the quality deterioration is mainly attributed to microbial spoilage, resulting in sensory modifications and thus sensory rejection. However, when storage at subzero temperatures is used (such as freezing) then the quality deterioration is correlated with physical and chemical reactions, such as dehydration and lipid oxidation, respectively, defining the end of shelf life. Based on the properties of the final product and the mode of action of the applied hurdles, the following categorization of hurdle preserved fish products can be proposed.

3.1. Intermediate and high moisture fish products

Intermediate moisture fish products are in a_w range between 0.9 and 0.6. In this case, a_w is the primary hurdle for microbial stability and safety. This kind of fish products are stabilized by additional hurdles, such as heating, preservatives, pH and competitive microflora. In the preparation of intermediate moisture foods, some water is removed

from the fresh food and the availability of the rest of water to microbial growth may be further reduced by the addition of suitable solutes (humectants). The production of intermediate moisture foods with the combined application of suitable antimicrobial and antimycotic agents may enable food storage for long periods at ambient temperatures, decreasing preservation cost and energy consumption (especially if the final a_w is lower than 0.85). In intermediate fish products with a_w values higher than 0.85, pH plays an important role in the control of spoilage organisms. At pH 5.0 or below, microbial growth—except for desirable strains such as *Lactobacillus*, is inhibited.

High moisture fish products are minimally processed fresh-like products. The a_w of the final product is above 0.9 and these foods are either chilled or frozen. Maintaining low temperature in the cold chain is energy consuming and demands high costs. It is also evident that the temperature fluctuations that occur in the actual cold chain may affect significantly the quality level and remaining shelf life of these products at any stage of the food supply chain. Therefore, besides the low temperature, additional hurdles should be applied in order to preserve quality and extend shelf life of the high moisture fish products (Erkmen & Bozoglu, 2016, pp. 166–179). Slightly low a_w levels can be achieved by the application of osmotic dehydration processing on fresh fish fillets (Tsironi, Salapa, & Taoukis, 2009; Tsironi & Taoukis, 2014). In this case, the final a_w is as low as 0.95, which may inhibit the growth of *Pseudomonas* spp., the dominant spoilage factor for aerobically packed, chilled Mediterranean fish (Neumeyer, Ross, & McMeekin, 1997). The pH of the osmotically treated fish products can be decreased by the incorporation of agents such as glucono- δ -lactone in the osmotic solution (Tsironi & Taoukis, 2012). This is an additional hurdle that acts synergistically to the low a_w and the refrigerated storage temperature, further delaying microbial growth and extending shelf life. A similar synergistic effect has been reported for the incorporation of carvacrol, nisin or other natural antimicrobials and plant extracts in the osmotic solution to be used for fish fillet osmotic treatment (Tsironi & Taoukis, 2010 and, 2012; Sofra, Tsironi, & Taoukis, 2018). Such minimal processes are cost and energy efficient and may provide food products with extended shelf life without affecting significantly the initial sensory properties (Erkmen & Bozoglu, 2016, pp. 166–179).

3.2. Fermented fish products

Fermented fish products (such as stinky mandarin fish in China) can be produced using hurdles which ensure that they are stable, high quality and safe at room temperature for extended periods. The microbial stability of fermented fish is achieved by the use of a combination of hurdles at several stages of the manufacturing process (Erkmen & Bozoglu, 2016, pp. 166–179). This type of preservation is directly connected to the biopreservation, which is used to extend the shelf life of refrigerated products by the inoculation of bacteria selected for their inhibition properties towards undesirable microorganisms. Lactic acid bacteria are in most cases used, due to their capability to produce a wide range of inhibitory compounds such as organic acids, hydrogen peroxide, diacetyl and bacteriocins. Furthermore, due to the association of biopreserved products with the fermentation process, they hold the GRAS (generally recognized as safe) status granted by the FDA (Leroi et al., 2006, pp. 399–425). Fish flesh undergoes a series of changes during the fermentation process, especially modifications in taste and texture. It has been reported that the texture of fermented mandarin fish muscle is closely related to the water content of fish flesh (Yang et al., 2017). According to Wang et al. (2019), aspartic acid and glutamic acid exert an important influence on the umami taste of fish sauce during fermentation. The combined application of fish fermentation by *Bacillus polymyxa* as a starter culture with the addition of salt may decrease histamine and other biogenic amines formation, as reported by Lee, Kung, Huang, Huang, and Tsai (2016).

3.3. Thermally treated fish products

Thermal treatment of fish products depends mainly on hurdle technology and the final products exhibit usually very long shelf life. Aguilera, Francke, Figueroa, Bornarat, and Cifuentes (1992) reported that addition of 6% salt and 0.2% sorbate at pH 5.7 when accompanied by heat treatment (10 min, 80 °C) increased the shelf life of minced pelagic fish to 15 days at 15 °C compared with less than 3 days for untreated samples. Choulitoudi et al. (2017) evaluated the combined application of hot smoking and edible coating based active packaging enhanced by the incorporation of rosemary essential oil and/or extract at refrigerated storage under vacuum on eel fillets. Although the antimicrobial activity of rosemary EO and extract was moderate against total viable count, *Pseudomonas* spp. and lactic acid bacteria, the combination of extract (200 ppm) with EO (2000 ppm) retarded significantly the formation of both primary and secondary oxidation products, indicating possible synergistic effect. High pressure processing has been combined with cold smoking (corresponding to a mild thermal treatment method for fish) by Erkan et al. (2011) and Gudbjornsdottir, Jonsson, Hafsteinsson, and Heinz (2010) in order to extend shelf life without the use of intense thermal treatment which would affect sensory profile and nutritional value of fish products.

3.4. Refrigerated fish products

The use of refrigeration is appropriate for perishable products such as fish. However, it has been reported that the temperature conditions in the actual cold chain often deviate from the recommended range. For this reason, the preservation of refrigerated fish products is questionable if low temperature is the only applied hurdle. During the past years, fish (mainly gutted fish and fillets) are stored under modified atmospheres (Tsironi, Tsevdou, Velliou, & Taoukis, 2008a and 2011) or in vacuum (Tsironi, Gogou, Velliou, & Taoukis, 2008b). It has been reported that the combined application of modified atmospheres with the low a_w (by applying osmotic dehydration) and the addition of nisin in the osmotic solution may significantly extend the shelf life of refrigerated gilthead seabream fillets during storage at 0–15 °C (Tsironi & Taoukis, 2010). A similar approach has also been proposed by Qian, Yang, Ye, and Xie (2018) for seafood products in general, by demonstrating the preservative effect of the combined application of quercetin-containing additives and modified atmospheric packaging on refrigerated (4 °C) Pacific white shrimp. This study concluded that this combination of hurdles may reduce the risk of disorders caused by biogenic amines. The study published by Lan et al. (2018) showed that different concentration of *Ginkgo biloba* leaf extract had variable effects on retaining the texture parameters of acceptability limit, inhibit lipid oxidation and protein degradation and microorganisms growth in silver pomfret (*Pampus argenteus*). Bono and Badalucco (2012) combined ozone treatment with MAP to extend the shelf life of striped red mullet. Ozonised slurry ice has been also evaluated for its applicability to preserve quality of fish during slaughtering and storage (Bono et al., 2017; Campos, Losada, Rodríguez, Aubourg, & Barros-Velázquez, 2006, 2005). Concentration of 2.5 mg/mL of *Ginkgo biloba* leaf extract was the optimum condition for the preservation of pomfret during storage in ice. A novel application of nonthermal processing of Mediterranean fish has been proposed by Tsironi, Maltezou, Tsevdou, Katsaros, and Taoukis (2015) and Tsironi et al. (2019) by the combined application of high pressure processing (600 MPa, 5min) and refrigerated storage of gilthead seabream and seabass fillets, which resulted in three-fold shelf life extension at 0–2 °C. Apart from storage, low temperatures must be applied on fish at all stages of production. The combined application of chilling with another hurdle such as the addition of antimicrobial agents or another disinfection technique may further inhibit microbial growth and extend shelf life. According to Álvarez, Feás, Barros-Velázquez, and Aubourg (2009) Álvarez, Feás, Barros-Velázquez, and Aubourg (2009) slaughtering and storage under flow ice and ozonised

flow ice may affect significantly the quality of blackspot seabream.

4. Modelling the combined effect of hurdles on fish preservation

Different types of mainly empirical microbial growth models have been used for the evaluation of the effect of preservation hurdles on quality and shelf life of food products. These are specific to the types of microorganism, physicochemical properties of food and the applied hurdles. Davey, Lin, and Wood (1978) expressed the thermal inactivation rate ($\ln k$) of *Clostridium Botulinum* as a linear function of $1/T$, pH and pH^2 . A similar approach has been reported by Cerf, Davey, and Sadoudi (1996) for the regression correlations of $\ln(k)$ as a function of $1/T$, pH, pH^2 and a_w (Rahman, 2015). Koutsoumanis and Sofos (2005) modelled the growth/no growth response of *Listeria monocytogenes* inoculated at different levels within the range 0.9–6.81 logcfu/g into tryptic soy broth as a function of temperature, pH, a_w and storage time, providing quantitative data about the combined effect of hurdles on growth of the target pathogen.

Tsironi and Taoukis (2014) proposed a modified Arrhenius-type predictive model for the evaluation of the effect of storage temperature (0–15 °C) and a_w on *Pseudomonas* spp. growth rate and shelf life of osmotically dehydrated gilthead seabream fillets during refrigerated storage. A first degree polynomial model was selected for the description of a_w as a function of osmotic solution concentration and processing time. Considering furthermore the safety aspects of fish preservation, Emborg and Dalgaard (2008) modelled the formation of histamine in tuna as a function of temperature, CO_2 in the package headspace, pH and NaCl content. Tsironi et al. (2008a) proposed a modified Arrhenius for predicting LAB growth and consequently quality and shelf life of MAP seabream fillets at different storage conditions (0–15 °C and 20–80% CO_2), as illustrated in Fig. 2. This model was validated at variable conditions by Tsironi et al. (2011). Tsironi and Taoukis (2010) reported significant shelf life extension in osmotically dehydrated and MAP gilthead seabream fillets during refrigerate storage. The preservative effect of the different hurdles was mathematically modelled and predictive shelf life models were developed at isothermal conditions (0–15 °C) and validated at variable conditions. The addition of nisin prolonged shelf life to 48 days at 0 °C, compared to 10 days of untreated (Control) samples (Fig. 3).

The mathematical models developed for the effect of hurdles on fish preservation are summarized in Table 1.

5. Conclusions

Hurdles used in food preservation can provide varying results depending on microbial stress reactions. These stress reactions or cross-

Fig. 2. Shelf life (d) of gilthead seabream fillets stored under MAP in the range 20–80% CO_2 and 0–15 °C, calculated using the combined Arrhenius-type model by Tsironi, Stamatiou, Giannoglou, Velliou, and Taoukis (2011). — Control aerobically packed, i.e. 0% CO_2 , - - - 25% CO_2 , . . . 50% CO_2 and - . - . 75% CO_2 .

Fig. 3. Hurdle effect on fish slices: Shelf life (d) of gilthead seabream fillets treated with osmotic dehydration (OD) with the addition of nisin (ODn), stored under aerobic conditions or under modified atmospheres (50% CO₂) at 0–15 °C, calculated by the mathematical models by Tsironi and Taoukis (2010). — Control, — OD, — MAP, — ODN, - - - MAP-OD and - - - MAP-ODn.

Table 1
Mathematical modelling of hurdle effect on fish preservation.

Fish product	Hurdles ^a	Mathematical model	Reference
Cod (<i>Gadus morhua</i>)	T, a _w , pH	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> growth (logistic)	Dalgaard et al. (1998)
Eel (<i>Anguilla Anguilla</i>) fillets	T, smoking, EC, rosemary EO, rosemary extract	Microbial growth (Baranyi)	Choulitoudi et al. (2017)
Gilthead seabream (<i>Sparus aurata</i>) fillets	T, a _w , MAP, nisin	Microbial growth (Baranyi) TVBN (1st order) Sensory scoring (zero order) Arrhenius (secondary model)	Tsironi and Taoukis (2010)
Gilthead seabream (<i>Sparus aurata</i>) fillets	T, MAP	Microbial growth (Baranyi) Sensory scoring (zero order) Arrhenius (secondary model)	Tsironi et al. (2008a); Tsironi et al. (2011)
Gilthead seabream (<i>Sparus aurata</i>) fillets	T, a _w , carvacrol, glucono-δ-lactone, citrox	Microbial growth (Baranyi) TVBN (1st order) Sensory scoring (zero order) Arrhenius (secondary model)	Tsironi and Taoukis (2012)
Gilthead seabream (<i>Sparus aurata</i>) fillets	T, a _w	Microbial growth (Baranyi) Modified Arrhenius (secondary)	Tsironi and Taoukis (2014)
Gilthead seabream (<i>Sparus aurata</i>) fillets	HP, T	Microbial growth (Baranyi) Colour (zero order) Sensory scoring (zero order) Arrhenius (secondary)	Tsironi et al. (2015)
Gilthead seabream (<i>Sparus aurata</i>) fillets	T, a _w	Microbial growth (Baranyi) TBARs (zero order) TVBN (1st order) Sensory scoring (zero order) Ratkowsky (secondary)	Tsironi and Taoukis (2017)
Gilthead seabream (<i>Sparus aurata</i>)	T, EC, <i>Satureja thymbra</i> EO, <i>Satureja thymbra</i> extract	Microbial growth (Baranyi)	Choulitoudi et al. (2016)
Greenland halibut (<i>Reinhardtius hippoglossoides</i>)	T, acetic acid, lactic acid	Microbial growth (square root)	Mejlholm and Dalgaard (2015)
Greenland halibut (<i>Reinhardtius hippoglossoides</i>)	T, pH, NaCl, phenol, acetic acid, lactic acid	Microbial growth (stochastic)	Mejlholm, Bøknæs, and Dalgaard (2015)
Lumpfish (<i>Cyclopterus lumpus</i>)	T, MAP, benzoic acid, citric acid	Microbial growth (square root)	Mejlholm and Dalgaard (2015)
Red mullet (<i>Mullus barbatus</i>)	T, MAP	Microbial growth (logistic) Ratkowsky, Arrhenius (secondary)	Koutsoumanis, Taoukis, Drosinos, and Nychas (2000)
Salmon (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	T, acetic acid, lactic acid	Microbial growth (square root)	Mejlholm and Dalgaard (2015)
Yellowfin tuna (<i>Thunnus albacares</i>)	pH, NaCl, MAP	Microbial growth (logistic) Histamine (logistic) Square root (secondary)	Emborg and Dalgaard (2008)
Yellowfin tuna (<i>Thunnus albacares</i>)	T, a _w	Microbial growth (Baranyi) TBARs (zero order) TVBN (1st order) Sensory scoring (zero order) Arrhenius (secondary)	Sofra et al. (2018)
Yellowfin tuna (<i>Thunnus albacares</i>)	T, VP	Microbial growth (Baranyi) Sensory scoring (zero order) Arrhenius (secondary)	Tsironi et al. (2008b)
Yellowfin tuna (<i>Thunnus albacares</i>)	T, MAP, pH	Microbial growth (Baranyi) Histamine (logistic)	Emborg and Dalgaard (2008)

^a EC: edible coating, MAP: modified atmosphere packaging; T: temperature; VP: vacuum packaging.

tolerance may not exist when combined hurdles are used. There are three possible effects by the application of hurdles in food systems: (i) additive, (ii) synergistic, or (ii) antagonistic effect. For this reason, the application of hurdle technology should be complemented by predictive microbiology tools and HACCP and Good Manufacturing Practices for process optimization (Erkmen & Bozoglu, 2016, pp. 166–179). The combined application of soft hurdles will not only inhibit effectively microbial growth, but also enable the preservation of the sensory parameters of the target fish product, compared to the application of a single but more intense preservative factor (Lroi et al., 2006, pp. 399–425).

In general, minimal processing methods have shown the potential to further prolong the shelf life of fish products by the combined application of preservative hurdles such as low storage temperature, addition of antimicrobials and/or antioxidants, water activity, pH, and high pressure processing with alternative packaging, such as modified atmospheres (Bouletis, Arvanitoyannis, & Hadjichristodoulou, 2017; Sivertsvik, Jeksrud, & Rosnes, 2002).

Future research should be focused on initiating hurdle technologies

for optimum active and smart packaging systems by incorporating multiple active components or active and smart functionalities in one system (Ahmed et al., 2017; Tsironi & Taoukis, 2018).

Acknowledgment

This Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Grant agreement 872217.

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